

IR28211-43-1-1, all characters but leaf dry weight differed significantly among grades. Differences in IR28211-43-1-1 were greater because differences among embryo weights were larger.

Mean data show significant differences among grades for all traits except plant height and specific leaf weight. The coefficient of variation for growth parameters was much lower for HD grains (Table 2) than for poor and good grains. This indicates that intravarietal or intragenotype variation can be lessened by planting HD grains. □

Table 2. Coefficient of variation for growth parameters of different grain grades at 25 d after sowing.

Grain grade	Coefficient of variation						
	Plant height	Tiller no.	Leaf area	Specific leafweight	Leaf dry weight	Culm dry weight	Total dry weight
	<i>IR30</i>						
Poor	13.2	48.0	33.6	31.6	30.4	31.2	30.8
Good	10.1	35.6	31.7	25.8	27.1	26.4	26.7
High density	11.3	22.1	27.2	20.2	20.3	22.3	21.3
	<i>IR32385-37-3-3</i>						
Poor	12.0	34.4	40.1	40.0	76.3	38.2	57.2
Good	4.4	16.1	21.5	16.7	16.5	17.5	17.0
High density	6.7	17.3	18.2	17.4	16.8	17.1	16.9
	<i>IR28211-13-1-1</i>						
Poor	23.0	21.7	25.1	21.0	21.1	21.1	25.1
Good	6.1	18.4	23.4	19.1	19.9	18.3	23.9
High density	3.5	15.8	16.8	16.1	19.2	13.1	13.1

Path analysis of rice grain yield under rainfed lowland conditions

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We examined direct and indirect associations of four yield components with grain yield in drought-tolerant lines MDU1, Brown gora, BR319-1, OS4, E45, C22, OS6, IR12979-24-1-8, UPLRi-5, UPLRi-7, Azucena, N22, and Kalakeri and local check PMK1 grown in semidry conditions in 1988.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Productive tillers had high direct effects on grain yield (see table). Panicle length and flowering duration had moderate direct effects. The effect

of plant height was slightly negative.

Productive tillers appear to be the most reliable character to use in selecting genotypes under rainfed condition. □

Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects of yield components on grain yield under rainfed lowland semidry conditions.^a Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Variable	Flowering duration	Plant height	Panicle length	Productive tillers	Total correlation with yield
Flowering duration	<u>0.250</u>	0.006	0.161	-0.255	0.162
Plant height	-0.085	<u>-0.016</u>	-0.150	-0.109	-0.361
Panicle length	0.130	0.008	<u>0.310</u>	-0.598	-0.150
Productive tillers	-0.063	0.002	-0.183	<u>0.992</u>	0.748**

^a Residual effect = 0.471. Underlined correlations indicate direct effects. ** = significant at P = 0.01.

Varietal differences in rice ratoon performance

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The success of rice ratooning depends primarily on the variety used. We compared medium-duration rice varieties Ponni and Bhavani in sandy clay loam soils during the wet season.

The main crop was harvested 15 cm from ground level and the stubble fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Bhavani was significantly superior to Ponni on all growth and yield attributes (see table). The Bhavani ratoon crop yielded 2.8 t/ha—50% of its main crop

yield. Ponni produced 1.8 t/ha, 38% of its main crop yield. Straw yield in Bhavani ratoon was also higher. □

Growth and yield attributes of rice ratoon crop in Madurai, India during the wet season.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Ratoon tillers/hill	Productive tillers/m ²	Filled grains/panicle	Thousand-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Ponni	69.7	9.4	319.2	59.4	15.5	1.8	2.3
Bhavani	74.0	11.9	414.2	66.2	20.8	2.8	3.4
LSD (0.05)	1.7	0.4	9.5	2.6	0.11	0.2	0.3